

Short communication

First record of *Oxycarenus lavaterae* (Fabricius, 1787) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Oxycarenidae) for Albania

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Abstract. The first record of *Oxycarenus lavaterae* (Fabricius, 1787) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Oxycarenidae) for Albania is reported. Recent trends regarding the expansion of the distribution area of the species are discussed.

Key words: Heteroptera, Oxycarenidae, *Oxycarenus lavaterae*, distribution, new record, Europe, Mediterranean Region, Albania.

Oxycarenus lavaterae (Fabricius, 1787) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Oxycarenidae) is native to the Western Mediterranean Region (van der Heyden 2023). In the last decades, the species has expanded its area of distribution eastwards towards the Balkan Peninsula (Hoffmann 2020). According to Hoffmann (2020) and Aukema (2024) it has not been reported from Albania, yet.

Now, the first record of *O. lavaterae* for Albania can be reported: On 29.04.2023, a huge aggregation of the species (Fig. 1) was found on a tree trunk, seemingly *Tilia* sp., near Shtuf in the municipality of Shkodër, located in northwestern Albania near the border with Montenegro. Four related photographs were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Jędrusiak 2023).

Hoffmann (2020) mentioned that *O. lavaterae* had not been reported for Kosovo, so far; Aukema (2024) has not listed the country in the list of the distribution of the species. Taking the recent expansion of *O. lavaterae* and the fact that it is also present in the neighbouring countries Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia (Hoffmann 2020; Aukema 2024) into account, it seems only a matter of time until the species will be found in Kosovo as well.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Kacper Jędrusiak (Poland) for allowing me to use his photo of *O. lavaterae* to illustrate this note.

References

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Fig. 1. Aggregation of *Oxycarenus lavaterae* (Fabricius, 1787), near Shtuf, municipality of Shkodër, Albania (photo: Kacper Jędrusiak).

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Received: 4 June 2024
Accepted: 26 June 2024